

AMERIKA ADABIYOTIDA AMIR TEMUR SIYMOZI

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Annotasiya: *Jahon tarixida chuqur iz qoldirgan buyuk sarkarda - Amir Temur shaxsiga murojat, u haqida yaratilgan badiiy asarlar, ulardagi tarixiy haqiqat aks etilishi katta ahamiyatga ega. Mazkur izlanishimizda biz Robert Govardning Amir Temur shaxsiga bag'ishlangan asari haqida fikr va mulohazalarimizni bildirganmiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Amerika adabiyoti, Amir Temur siymosi, syujet, sarkarda, bunyodkor.*

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Аннотация: *Большое значение имеет обращение к личности Амира Темура, великого полководца, оставившего глубокий след в мировой истории, и созданным о нем художественным произведениям, отражающим в них историческую правду. В этом исследовании мы высказали свои мысли и мнения о работе Роберта Ховарда, посвященной личности Амира Темура.*

Ключевые слова: *американская литература, образ Амира Темура, сюжет, военачальник, творец.*

Annotation: *It is of great importance to refer to the personality of Amir Temur, the great leader who left a deep mark in world history, and the artistic works created about him, reflecting the historical truth in them. In this research, we expressed our thoughts and opinions about Robert Howard's work dedicated to the personality of Amir Temur.*

Key words: *American literature, image of Amir Temur, plot, warlord creator*

Amir Temur haqida xorij adabiyotida yuzlab asarlar, xususan, Amerika adabiyotining yirik vakillaridan biri Robert Govard ham Sohibqiron haqida o'zining "Samarqand hukmdori" asarida, ushbu buyuk zotning o'z saltanatini barpo etishdagi sa'yi-harakatlari, yuksak harbiy zakovati, yaratuvchilik istedodi xususida ma'lumotlar bergan. O'zbek adabiyotshunosligida mazkur asar haqida ilk bor M.Yakubov¹ o'zining ilmiy tadqiqotida batafsil ma'lumot bergan.

Robert Govard (1906-1936) amerikalik yozuvchi, turli janrlarda ijod qilgan adiblardan biri. Asosan Govard ijodi vikinglar, arablar, umuman harbiy yurushlarga bag'ishlangan hikoyalardan iborat bo'lgan. Govard tarixni yaxshi ko'rar va shu sabab tarixiy hikoyalarga ko'p murojat etadi. Ayniqsa sarkarda va kuchli shaxslar haqida asar yozishni ma'qul ko'rgan

¹ Yakubov M. Инглизбабон адабиётда Амир Темур сиймоси. Фал.фан.док. (PhD) дисс... – Бухоро. 2021.

bo'lishi kerakki, uning ko'plab ijod na'munalari orasida Sharq hikoyalari ruknida 9 bobdan iborat "Lord of Samarcand" (Oriental Stories, Spring 1932)² (keyingi misollar shu manbadan keltiriladi) Samarqand hukdori deb nomlangan asar paydo bo'ldi. Asar Amir Temur bu zotning o'sha davr egallagan mavqei, sohibqiron egallagan hududlarda shahar va qishloqlarning chiroyli qad rostlab turishi, ayniqsa barpo etgan saltanatning poytaxti bo'lmish, Samarqand muallif qalamida faxr ila namoyish etilgan. Turk sultoni Boyazidga qarshi bo'lgan jang va Xitoyga rejalashtirilayotgan yurish tavsilotlari ham bayon etilgan. Asarda Robert Amir Temur haqida shunday yozadi: "Timour, the Servant of God, by the favor of Allah, Amir of Tatory." - Temur, Yaratganning quli, Olloh inoyati ila, Tatariya Amiri. Amir Temur hukmronligi davrida Samarqand qanday qad rostlagani yuzasidan ham ma'lumot berib o'tadi: "You have seen lands and seas no Frank has beheld," said Ak Boga, "and rivers and towns and caravan trails. Now you shall gaze upon the glory of Samarcand, which the lord Timour found a town of dried brick and has made a metropolis of blue stone and ivory and marble and silver filigree." Tarjimasi : Sen hech bir frank ko'rmagan yerlarni, dengizlarni, daryolarni va shaharlarni hamda karvonlarni ko'rasan. Samarqand shuhratiga amin bulasan, oliy hazratim Temur pishgan g'ishtdan qurilgan shaharni moviy tosh, fil suyagi, marmar va kumush filigrandan yasalgan ajoyib maskanga aylantirdi.

Govard ushbu fikrlarini davom etgan holda Samarqand saroyi, shaharning keng ko'chalari, savdo qilayotgan turli mamlakatlar va qavmlar vakillari bilan to'la shovqinli bozor haqida so'z yuritadi. Bu yerda yovvoyi arablar, bezovta bo'layotgan ozg'in siriyaliklar, semiz laganbardor yahudiylar, salla kiygan hindular, toliqqan persiyaliklar, eski juldurvaqa kiyimda qaddini g'oz tutgan shubhali avg'onlar, va yana bir qancha notanish millatlar vakillari, Uzoq Sharqdan va sirli shimoldan yetib kelganlar, baquvvat kalta bo'yli beparvo mo'g'ullar, ipak kiyimda bo'lgan ko'zi qisq xitoyliklar, baland bo'yli janjalkash uyg'urlar, yuzi yumaloq qipchoqlar, ko'zi kichik qirg'izlar, hatto g'arbda umuman noma'lum bo'lgan har xil irq vakillari savdogarlari yig'ilgan edilar. Butun Sharq mamlakatlari Samarqand darvozasiga qarab yopirilyotgan edi : "They rode through the wide winding streets, past palace and market and mosque, and bazaars thronged with the people of a hundred tribes and races, bartering, disputing, shouting. The Scotsman saw hawk-faced Arabs, lean apprehensive Syrians, fat fawning Jews, turbaned Indians, languid Persians, ragged swaggering but suspicious Afghans, and more unfamiliar forms; figures from the mysterious reaches of the north, and the far east; stocky Mongols with broad inscrutable faces and the rolling gait of an existence spent in the saddle; slant-eyed Cathayans in robes of watered silk; tall quarrelsome Vigurs; round-faced Kipchaks; narrow-eyed Kirghiz; a score of races whose existence the West did not guess. All the Orient flowed in a broad river through the gates of Samarcand."

Asarda shotlandiyalik savdogar Amir Temur bilan uchrashadi va Sohibqironni shuday tasvirlaydi: "... this, then, was the mysterious Tamerlane, who was already becoming a mythical figure in Western lore. He saw a man as tall as himself, gaunt but heavy-boned, with a wide sweep of shoulders and the Tatar's characteristic depth of chest. His face was not as dark as Ak Boga's, nor did his black magnetic eyes slant; and he did not sit cross-legged as a Mongol sits.

² http://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Author:Robert_Ervin_Howard

There was power in every line of his figure, in his clean-cut features, in the crisp black hair and beard, untouched with gray despite his sixty-one years. ... He was closer to the basic Turanian rootstock ...” Tarjimasi “ ... mana u, G’arb manbalarda afsonaga aylangan, o’sha sirli Temur manbalarda afsonaga aylangan, o’sha sirli Temur. Mak Diz o’zidek baland bo’yli, ozg’indan kelgan lekin og’ir suyakli, yelkalari katta va tatarlarga xos bag’ri keng bir odamni ko’rayotgani. Uning yuzi Ak Boga yuzidek qoradan kelgan emas edi, biroq ko’zlari qora edi, u mo’g’ullar kabi oyoqlarini chalishtirib o’tirmagandi. Uning har bir harakati qudratidan nishona edi, qalin qora sochi va soqoliga, 61 yoshda bo’lsa ham, oq tushmagan edi. ... U asl turonlik edi.”

Keyinchalik, aynan shu ritsar (Donald Mak Diza) Amir Temur bilan bir safda bir qancha janglarda ishtirok etib, Sohibqiron jasoratiga tan berib shunday deydi: “When rivers run uphill, Timour will flee ...”

Govard Boyazidning asosiy dushmani Temur ekanligi va turk sultoni unga bepisand tarzda po’pisa qilib bir qancha javobsiz qolgan nomalar jo’natgani, ayni damda karvonlar qudratli qo’shinlari sarosimada tatar nayzalari ostida qochib ketganliklari haqida xabarlar yetkazganliklari quyidagicha izohlaydi: “Somewhere in the misty mazes of the East moved his arch-foe Timour, and to him Bayazid sent missives of threat and mockery. No response was forthcoming, but word came along the caravans of a mighty marching and a great war in the south; of the plumed helmets of India scattered and flying before the Tatar spears.”

“... On his head was the jeweled turban of sovereignty, in his hand the gem-starred scepter of his vanished empire. He did not touch the great golden goblet before him. Many and many a time had he exulted over the agony of the vanquished, with much less mercy than was now shown him; now the unfamiliar bite of defeat left him frozen.” Tarjimasi : “Temur uni yaxshi kutib oldi va unga hech qanday shikast yetkazmadi” dedi, yangilikni olib kelgan saroy amaldori. “Sulton bazmda ishtirok etadi” ...Sulton qimmat baho toshlar bilan bezatilgan buyuk hukmdor sallasida va qo’lida endilikda zabt etilgan saltanat hassasi bilan o’tirgandi. U oldida katta oltin kosaga qo’lini ham tekkizgani yo’q. Qancha qanchalab u jon talvasasida kurashayotganlar ustidan kuldi, ularga zarracha muruvvat ko’rsatmasdan, binobarin hozir unga katta ehtirom ko’rsatilayotgan edi. Unga ilgari notanish bo’lgan mag’lubiyat alami uni ich etini tirnardi.”

Hikoya yakunida Amir Temurning har qanday tadbirni amalga oshirishdan oldin ‘yetti marta o’lchab keyin kesadigan’ siyosatini madh etib, bu zotning ushbu xususiyatlariga shunday ta’rif beradi: “When other men looked days ahead, Timour looked years;” ya’ni boshqalar bir necha kunni ko’zlab ish tutsalar Amir Temur olis kelajakni o’ylab tadbir qiladi.

Amerika adabiyotining yirik vakili Robert Govardning ‘Samarqand Hukmdori’ asarida Sohibqironning buyuk saltanatini barpo etishdagi sa’y- harakatlari, yuksak harbiy zakovati, yaratuvchilik iste’dodiga oid ajoyib dalillar keltirilganki, buni asar mazmunidan bemalol anglab yetish mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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